

Supplementary Material

Archaeal signalling networks - new insights into the structure and function of histidine kinases and response regulators of the methanogenic archaeon *Methanosarcina acetivorans*

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Table S1: Microbial strains

Strain	Genotype	Reference
<i>E. coli</i> strains		
<i>E. coli</i> DH5 α	F ⁻ <i>endA1 glnV44 thi-1 recA1 relA1 gyrA96 deoR nupG purB20</i> ϕ 80d <i>lacZ</i> Δ M15 Δ (<i>lacZYA-argF</i>)U169, <i>hsdR17</i> (r _K ⁻ m _K ⁺), λ ⁻	(Hanahan, 1983)
<i>E. coli</i> BI21 (DE3)	F ⁻ <i>ompT gal dcm lon hsdS_B</i> (r _B ⁻ m _B ⁻) λ (DE3 [<i>lacI lacUV5-T7p07 ind1 sam7 nin5</i>]) [<i>malB</i> ⁺] _{K-12} (λ ^S)	(Studier & Moffatt, 1986)
<i>E. coli</i> Nissle 1917	serotype O6:K5:H1	(Grozdanov <i>et al.</i> , 2004)
<i>E. coli</i> C43 (DE3)	F ⁻ <i>ompT hsdS_B</i> (r _B ⁻ m _B ⁻) <i>gal dcm</i> (DE3)	(Miroux & Walker, 1996)
<i>E. coli</i> TKR 2000	Δ <i>kdpFABCDE trkA405 trkD1 atp706</i>	(Kollmann & Altendorf, 1993)
<i>M. acetivorans</i> strains		
<i>M. acetivorans</i> WWM73	Δ <i>hpt::PmcrB-tetR-ϕC31-int-attP</i>	(Guss <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

Table S2: Vectors and plasmids used in this study

Plasmid	Characteristic	Reference
pASK-IBA3	Expression vector, heterologous overexpression in <i>E. coli</i> , Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	IBA Lifescience GmbH
pACYCDuet-1	Expression vector, heterologous overexpression and coexpression in <i>E. coli</i> , His-tag and S-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	Novogene Co, Ltd.
pET21a(+)	Expression vector, heterologous overexpression in <i>E. coli</i> , T7-tag and His-tag, T7 promoter, Amp ^R	Novogene Co, Ltd.
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of MA_4377 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>SacII/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	(Sexauer, 2021)
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-CHPK	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of MA_4377 (CHASE-HK domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1R2	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated cytosolic MA_4377 (HK-R2 domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	(Sexauer, 2021)
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK _{H497Q} R1 _{D818N} R2	pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1R2 derivate with amino acid exchange: His497 to Gln and Asp818 to Asn, obtained by site-directed mutagenesis	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated cytosolic MA_4377 (HK-R1 domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA4_377-PK _{H497Q} R1	pASK-IBA3-MA4_377-PKR1 derivate with amino acid exchange: His497 to Gln, synthetic gene	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA4_377-PK	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated cytosolic MA_4377 (only HK domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	(Sexauer, 2021)
pASK-IBA3-MA4_377-PK _{H497Q}	pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK derivate with amino acid exchange: His497 to Gln, Synthetic gene	This study

pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-R1	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated cytosolic MA_4377 (only R1 domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>XbaI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-R2	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated cytosolic MA_4377 (only R2 domain) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>XbaI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_0863(rdmS) _{O216K}	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of MA_0863 (rdmS) with amino acid exchange (Pyl216 to Lys) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>SacII/PstI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	(Kwiatkowski, 2013)
pASK-IBA3-MA_2082	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of MA_2082 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of MA_2013 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NcoI</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_2013-PK	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of truncated MA_2013 (without R1 and HPT) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013-R1	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated MA_2013 (only R1) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013-HPT	pASK-IBA3 derivate, coding region of truncated MA_2013 (only HPT) from <i>M. acetivorans</i> with C-terminal Strep-tag II, <i>tet</i> promoter, Amp ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_0016	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_0016 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_0018	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_0018 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_1268	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_1268 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study

pACYC-Duet1-MA_1269	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_1269 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_1366	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_1366 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_1468	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_1468 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_1469	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_1469 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_2445	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_2445 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_2012	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_2012 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_2861	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_2861 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_3068	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_3068 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pACYC-Duet1-MA_4376 (R3)	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_4376 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>SacI/SalI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	(Sexauer, 2021)
pACYC-Duet1-MA_4671	pACYCDuet-1 derivate, coding region of MA_4671 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> at <i>BamHI/NdeI</i> with N-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Cm ^R	This study
pET21a(+)-MA_4375 (<i>msrX</i>)	pET21a (+) derivate, coding region of MA_4375 from <i>M. acetivorans</i> with C-terminal His-tag, T7 promoter, Amp ^R	(Sexauer, 2021)

Table S3: Oligonucleotids used in this study

Oligonucleotids	Sequence (5' → 3')
Oligonucleotids for sequencing	
pASK-IBA3-seq-fwd	CGCAGTAGCGGTAAACG
pASK-IBA3-seq-rev	GAGTTATTTTACCACTCCCT
pACYC-duet1-seq-fwd	TCTCCCTTATGCGACTCCTG
pACYC-duet1-seq-rev	GGGTTATGCTAGTTATTGCTCAGC
Oligonucleotids for expression plasmids	
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-fwd	GCTATCCGCGGCATGAATGTGAGTAGAAAAATTCT
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-rev	GCATACCATGGCCTCTTCGACAATAAGAATTTCTTTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-CHKP-fwd	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGATATGAATGTGAGTAGAAAAATTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-CHKP-rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACTCTGAGCTTCCCTATTTTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1R2-fwd	GCTATCCGCGGCAGGTTGAATTCCGATAAGGTAA
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1R2-rev	GCATACCATGGCCTCTTCGACAATAAGAATTTCTTTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1-fwd	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGCTAGGTTGAATTCCGATAAG
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PKR1-rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACGGAACTGAACTTACCTG
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK-fwd	GCTATCCGCGGCAGGTTGAATTCCGATAAGGTAA
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK-rev	GCGCCATGGCCTGTGAGGGGAATTG
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK für QC	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGCTATGAGGTTGAATTCCG
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-PK für QC	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACGCTTTGTGAGGGGAATTG
pASK-IBA-MA_4377-R1-fwd	ATGAATAGTTCGACAAAAATTAGTCTTGTGCTTGTAGTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-R1-rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACTGAACTGAACTTACCTG
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-R2-fwd	ATGAATAGTTCGACAAAAATTGGTAAGTTCAGTTTCGAC
pASK-IBA3-MA_4377-R2-rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACTTCTTCGACAATAAGAATTTCTTTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_0863(rdmS) _{0216K} -fwd	GGACCGCGGAAAAAAGTTTCGATATAAATC

pASK-IBA3- MA_0863(rdmS) _{0216K} - rev	GGACTGCAGTTATTTTTCGAACTCCGGGTGGCTCCAAGACTCTATTTGAT TCATG
pASK-IBA3-MA_2082- fwd	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGATATGGAAGGAAAAGTCTGAGAAATTCTGGTA TTGAG
pASK-IBA3-MA_2082- rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACTCTCGACGCCACAGGGA
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013- fwd	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGAAGTGTGCGGTTTAAAAAAC
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013- rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACGACAGATCTGTTTTTCCAG
pACYC-duet1- MA_2013-PK-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGTGCGGTTTAAAAAAC
pACYC-duet1- MA_2013-PK-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCACTAGCATACTAACAGGCTTTC
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013- R1-fwd	ATTCGAGCTCGGTACCCGGGCGATGGTGAAAAGAGGGG
pASK-IBA3-MA_2013- R1-rev	GTGGCTCCAAGCGCTGAGACCTATACTTTCCAGGTCCAG
pACYC-duet1- MA_0016-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGGCAAGAGTAATGATC
pACYC-duet1- MA_0016-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATTAATTTGGTTCAGCAATTTTTTAATTAC
pACYC-duet1- MA_0018-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGCCTGAAATCCTGATC
pACYC-duet1- MA_0018-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATCAACCAGGAGAATTCGTTG
pACYC-duet1- MA_1268-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGAAAACAAAGGTAGCTG
pACYC-duet1- MA_1268-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATTATTTTGACGGTAGTTTCAC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1269-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGGAAACATGGACGGCATTAAAC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1269-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATTAAGTAAGATTTACGACTTCAAGCC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1366-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGCATAACATCAATCTTGAC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1366-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATCAAATCCGACTACGTCTC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1468-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGGACAAAGCAAAGATTC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1468-rev	TATCCAATTGAGATCTGCCATTATTCTTCAGTTACTTTACCC
pACYC-duet1- MA_1469-fwd	ACCATCATCACCACAGCCAGATGAAAAAAGCAAAAATTCTGGTTGTTG

Table S4: Sequences of 53 putative HK and 15 RR of *M. acetivorans*. The protein name corresponds to the old locus tag. The new locus tag and the accession number of the protein in the uniprot database is displayed in the table. For the Alignment (Figure S2) and the phylogenetic tree (Figure 1A) the aminoacid sequence of the HisKA domain was employed. For the alignment (Figure S3) the amino acid sequence of the REC domain was employed.

Protein	New locus tag	Organism	Accession number	database
MA0014	MA_RS00065	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TUQ1	UniProt
MA0203	MA_RS01090	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TU70	UniProt
MA0490	MA_RS02555	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TTE7	UniProt
MA0551	MA_RS25000	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TT86	UniProt
MA0552	MA_RS02905	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TT85	UniProt
MA0619	MA_RS03260	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TT21	UniProt
MA0620	MA_RS03265	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TT20	UniProt
MA0758	MA_RS03960	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TSN7	UniProt
MA0759	MA_RS03965	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TSN6	UniProt
MA0777	MA_RS04070	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TSL9	UniProt
MA0863 (RdmS)	MA_RS04495	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TSD5	UniProt
MA0970	MA_RS24390	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TS36	UniProt
MA1149	MA_RS05985	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRM6	UniProt
MA1267	MA_RS06580	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRB3	UniProt
MA1270	MA_RS06595	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRB0	UniProt
MA1274	MA_RS06615	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRA6	UniProt
MA1322	MA_RS06850	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TR62	UniProt
MA1463	MA_RS24430	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQS7	UniProt
MA1470	MA_RS07625	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQS0	UniProt
MA1627	MA_RS08450	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQC1	UniProt
MA1628	MA_RS08455	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQC0	UniProt
MA1630	MA_RS08465	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQB8	UniProt
MA1645	MA_RS08530	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQA5	UniProt
MA1646	MA_RS08535	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQA4	UniProt
MA1704	MA_RS08850	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQ48	UniProt
MA1739	MA_RS09030	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQ13	UniProt
MA1844	MA_RS24495	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPR2	UniProt
MA1878	MA_RS09795	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPM8	UniProt
MA1957	MA_RS10200	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPF6	UniProt
MA1991	MA_RS24525	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPC2	UniProt
MA2013	MA_RS10480	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPA1	UniProt
MA2082	MA_RS10815	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TP40	UniProt
MA2256	MA_RS11710	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TNM8	UniProt
MA2266	MA_RS11765	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TNL9	UniProt
MA2294	MA_RS11915	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TNJ1	UniProt
MA2348	MA_RS12170	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TNE0	UniProt
MA2553	MA_RS13275	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TMU8	UniProt
MA2555	MA_RS13285	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TMU6	UniProt
MA2732	MA_RS14295	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TMC7	UniProt
MA2757	MA_RS28770	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TMA7	UniProt
MA2784	MA_RS28790	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TM82	UniProt
MA2890	MA_RS15160	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TLY2	UniProt

MA3066	MA_RS16035	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TLH0	UniProt
MA3346	MA_RS17465	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TKQ3	UniProt
MA3368	MA_RS25835	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TKN3	UniProt
MA3370	MA_RS24765	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TKN1	UniProt
MA3405	MA_RS17780	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TKK0	UniProt
MA3481	MA_RS18195	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TKC7	UniProt
MA3543	MA_RS24775	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TK73	UniProt
MA3962	MA_RS20675	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TJ26	UniProt
MA4026	MA_RS21010	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TIW4	UniProt
MA4377	MA_RS22890	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8THY1	UniProt
MA4561 (MsmS)	MA_RS23780	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8THF6	UniProt
MA_0016	MA_RS00075	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TUP9	UniProt
MA_0018	MA_RS00090	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TUP7	UniProt
MA_1268	MA_RS06585	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRB2	UniProt
MA_1269	MA_RS06590	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TRB1	UniProt
MA_1366	MA_RS07090	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TR18	UniProt
MA_1468	MA_RS07615	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQS2	UniProt
MA_1469	MA_RS07620	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TQS1	UniProt
MA_2012	MA_RS10475	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TPA2	UniProt
MA_2861	MA_RS15020	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TM09	UniProt
MA_3068	MA_RS16045	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TLG8	UniProt
MA_4376	MA_RS22885	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8THY2	UniProt
MA_4671	MA_RS11705	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TNM9	UniProt
MA_2445	MA_RS12700	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TN48	UniProt
MA_0015	MA_RS00070	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TUQ0	UniProt
MA_3057	MA_RS15990	<i>M. acetivorans</i>	Q8TLH9	UniProt

Figure S1: Genomic distribution of HK and RR in the genome of *M. acetivorans*. Genomic distribution of histidine kinases (HK = Histidine Kinase, HHK = hybrid histidine kinase, REC-HK = histidine kinase with N-terminal REC domain) and response regulators (RR = response regulator with output domain, REC only = response regulator with only REC domain) in the genome of *M. acetivorans*. The genome of *M. acetivorans* (NC_003552.1) was obtained from the NCBI database and analysed using the online tool PROKSEE (<https://proksee.ca/>) (Grant *et al.*, 2023).

MA_type 1A	MA3405	NM	SH ----- ELKTP	LNSIIG----F----SDLLKEETAGPLNEKQSRVYQFISSSGKN	45
	MA2294	SM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDMLLTQNFGLNKKQLRYVNNISVSGNH	45
	MA3962	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSVIG----F----SDLLLEGAFGLNPKQSKYVNNILISGKN	45
	MA1149	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNAVIG----F----SDLLLSETAGPLNEKQKRYTENISKSGSH	45
	MA2555	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDLLYEKIYGDLENEKQLKAVGNISRSQKH	45
	MA1739	NI	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDLLCEQIFGELNEKQLRYVMDAFLSKSGKH	45
	MA3368	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDMLYEQAYGELNKRQLRAIGNISSSGKH	45
	MA2553	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDLLYEKVYGELNKLKQTKAVGNISNSGKH	45
	MA4377	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNSIIG----F----SDILIEKRVFVGELENEKQLKYVNNISGSGKH	45
	MA2348	NM	SH ----- ELRTP	LNAVIG----F----ADILNEEGFGPLNKKQKRFVGNISTSGKH	45
no type	MA0777	--	-----	-----	0
MA_type 1B	MA1957	TV	SH ----- ELKTP	LNSIIG----F----SDLLLEDSSGKLSERQARYINNISISGKH	45
	MA2256	TM	SH ----- ELRTP	LTAIIG----F----SELMLGEATGEFDELNRKFLGHISNSGKH	45
	MA2013	NM	SH ----- EIRTP	MNAVIG----M----LEMLLETS---LTDEQREYLQLAHASAES	42
MA_type 1C	MA1270	VS	SH ----- DLQEP	LRMIAS---Y---LQLLQRRYQGELDERADKYIYFAVDGASR	45
MA_type 2	RdmS	--	-----	-----EDQQQKAIDTVINSSER	17
	MsmS	EF	VE ----- EMMFP	EK--AE---Y---GEIMDYETLYAIDSQQQKAVNTFIHYSEK	43
MA_type 3	MA0203	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNRSREDIKDSEVLEAFRESQDR	45
	MA0490	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLEAEKFSDE-----KMLESFRESQNR	39
	MA0551	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNQ-----KEVLEAFRESQNR	39
	MA0552	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNREDIKDSEILEAFRESQDR	45
	MA0619	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLEAEKFSDE-----RTLEAFRESQNR	39
	MA0620	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLQAEKFEFR-----EVIEAFRESQNR	39
	MA0758	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRD-----KDVLEAFRESQSR	39
	MA0759	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRD-----KEVLEAFRESQSR	39
	MA0970	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRGKKNIEDSKILEAFRESQDR	45
	MA1274	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRSREHVEDSEVLNAFKESQER	45
	MA1322	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFGNKKYIMNSEVLDVAFRESQDR	45
	MA1470	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLELQAEKFDNL-----EVLEAFRESQNR	39
	MA1627	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQADKFDNP-----KVIEAFRESQNR	39
	MA1628	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRD-----KEVLEAFRESQNR	45
	MA1630	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFEFR-----KNVTEAFREGQNR	39
	MA1645	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNRENIKDNSEVLEAFRESQDR	45
	MA1646	EL	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQADLFKGGKTTITDSEVLKAFNESIDR	45
	MA1704	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSFEAEKSTDP-----EILEAFRETQNR	39
	MA1844	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLELQADKFKDR-----EVIEAFRESQNR	39
	MA1878	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQIDIFSNREICKTPEVIEAFRESQNR	45
	MA1991	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLQAEKFRD-----QEVLEAFRESQDR	39
	MA2082	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFRD-----KEVLEAFRESQNR	39
	MA2266	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLQAEYFSDP-----KVKESFKDSQNR	39
	MA2732	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLECDLSSG--TPDHKKIAEAFRESHNR	44
	MA2757	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEQFKNRECIKNSEVLEAFRESQAR	45
	MA2784	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFKDREDIKDSEVLEAFRESQDR	45
	MA3346	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNFSKHEVCKTPKVVFAFKESQDR	45
	MA3370	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAGKFNKHEIRDSEVLEAFRESQDR	45
	MA3481	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSMLSLQAEKFSDE-----ETLEAFRESQNR	39
	MA3543	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFNKREGIKDSEVMEAFRESQDR	45
MA4026	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFSHREAVPTLEILEAFRESQNR	45	
MA1267	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEKFEFR-----PTIRQAFRESQNR	39	
MA1463	EI	NH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLDLQAEQFSDK-----KVIEAFRESEN	39	
MA2890	EI	HH ----- RIKNN	LQ-----VSSLLSLQADKFKDK-----DVIEAFRESEN	39	
MA_CheA	MA0014	--	-----	-----RISTEQLDKL-MNLVGVINRSRVKELTGESKSK	34
	MA3066	GS	SHHFSESAASAKTP	LETQRQETIRVRTSNLDNI-MNLVGVINRGRLLQISQEQYNLP	59

Figure S2: Partial amino acid sequence alignment of HisKA domain of all putative HK of *M. acetivorans*. Accession numbers of the employed sequences are listed in Supplement Table S4, for the alignment only the amino acid sequences of the HisKA domain were taken. The Alignment was constructed using CUSTAL Omega and modified using PowerPoint. Conserved His residue is highlighted in bold with gray background. H-box region groups into four distinct groups (Ma_type 1 A/B/C, Ma_type 2, Ma_type 3 and MA_CheA). MA_type 1 is similar to the Type I HK of bacteria. As the amino acid arrangement differs within the group, the subgroups A, B and C were created. MA_type 2 kinases

are characterized by the absence of an H-box and MA_type 3 kinases cannot be grouped with a known type of bacterial kinases. MA_CheA are highly similar to bacterial CheA proteins.

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MA0016 -----MARVMIVDDAEFMRMVIDRILLKHGHE-VVAEVDGDEEAIQTYL-----E 44
MA0018 -----MPEILIVEDNLLNLVIEADLLKSCGY--DPKKAKNGFEALEVLS-----KV 44
MA1268 MKTKVAAKPIEILLVEDSEGVDGLIEEVFEEAKIRNNLHIVEDGEEAIFLFRGEKQFSGI 60
MA1269 METWTAFKPV DILLVEDDNKGDVGLIEEVFESSKVRNKLYVVEDGEEAVHFLLREGKFS DV 60
MA1366 -----KILIMGNGNNVHNNLQKVLEAENY--NVVSASDNFSAIETV-----NE 41
MA1468 -----MDKAKILVVEDQNI VALNLRNRLKNGMYI-VPTIAISGEEAIRKTE-----L 46
MA1469 -----MKKAKILVVEDQNI VALNIRNKLKNLGYT-VPGTASTGEEAIRKAE-----L 46
MA2012 -----KVLIAEDEPI SNLWLKNTLTRWGY--EAISTRDGYEAWEVLN-----ES 42
MA2013-R1 -----NVLFAEDHPINQKLI LGLLEKKGH--KLTLVTS GKDALDALS-----RR 42
MA2445 -----KVLIVDDKKNVELMEAYLAVEPY--DVI TAYGGKEAFQKV-----KE 41
MA2861 -----MKVLLVDDDPV FLELSKTFLEVFHDI-NSD TVESARQALEKLD-----E 43
MA3068 -----MAKVLIVDDTAFMRKLLKNILFGAGFD- IAGEAENGKQAVEMYK-----G 44
MA4376 -----MKEILIVEDNPMNMEILIDLLEFYGH--RVTEAEDGIKALERLA-----EK 44
MA4377-R1 -----LVLVVD DINSNELISVVLREAGY--STASLHNGKDVLEVA-----KK 41
MA4377-R2 -----KVLII D DENAVELLSSMIESEGF--EIVKAYSQAGLDKLF-----SE 42
MA4671 -----MEMKSILVVEDSPVILELISFFLTSSGY--ESRETGDGFDALKIAE-----EN 46
      ... :
MA0016 VKPDLVLM D IIMP-DMDGKEALQKLL LID-----PDAKVVMCSSLGQALITESMKIGAM 98
MA0018 KVD-LVLM D MELP-KMHGLELLQRIKCNP---ETQGIRVVAVTGHCDPESEQEFKAGCH 99
MA1268 SRPDI ILL D L NLP-KKDGREVL EEIKEDD---DLKNIPVVVLTTSKAEEDVLKSYNLHAN 116
MA1269 PRPDI ILL D L NLP-KKDGREVL EEIKEDD---DLKNIPVVVLTTSRAEEDI LESYKLHAN 116
MA1366 EKPD LVL D I T VYL-ETDGFEICRQLK DSP---RYWWIPI MMLSERNKTEDGIKAFDSGAD 97
MA1468 TTPDI LVL D I MLKGDMDGIEAARI I KSRF-----SAPVLYLTACTDIGILERAKLTEPA 100
MA1469 TNAD LVL D I MLKGDMDGIEAAREI KARL-----KIPVLYLTAYTDDETLERAKMTEPA 100
MA2012 DFPFVVI D WEMP-KMKGIEVCEKIKKDP---RLSSIIYI I LITGRDLTEDMEAGFKAGAD 98
MA2013-R1 DFD-AVLM D I QMP-GMDGLEATRRI RDPSSGVRRHNIPI I AFTARALKEDREKCFEAGMN 100
MA2445 EKPD I ILL D V MPM-EVNGYEVCKILKGNP---ETQFIPVLM L TALSELEDRIRGIEVGAD 97
MA2861 LSYD VVV S D Y MPM-YMDGISFLKTIRDKR-----INIPFILFTGVGKEEIKSQAIENGVD 97
MA3068 LKPD VVT M D V MPM-EMTGIDALKQIKALD-----KDAKIVMCTAIGQENIVKTAIKLGAR 98
MA4376 KFD- I ILL D M QLP-KMDGLEVLDRIKKNP---ATADIPVIAVTAHAMKGSEEHFIEMGCV 99
MA4377-R1 LKPD VIT I D V LLP-DTSGWNV LKQLKSDL---DTTSIPVLI I SVTDNNE---LGVALGAT 94
MA4377-R2 QQPD I ILL D L MPM-EISGF E I I SRLRDGE---QTKDIPLIVCTAGEFTEKNIEKLN GELK 98
MA4671 RFD-LILL D K QLP-GFDGLEVLK KIKKIF---EIRKTSVIALMAHAMQGD EDRFLKAGCN 101
      : * * . : .:
MA0016 GF-----I IKPFEPDGMLDVIK K IAEPN----- 121
MA0018 AV-----LSKPINFDFLFGAQVKEFLTATNSPG----- 126
MA1268 AY-----VTKPVDFDQFIRVIKSI ED FWLEVVKLPSK----- 148
MA1269 AY-----VTKPVDFDQFIKVIKSI ENFWLEVVNLT----- 146
MA1366 DY-----ITMPFNPLEL KARVGMIL----- 117
MA1468 GY-----ISKPFKEKDLVSNIEVALQKNKL-GKVTEE----- 131
MA1469 GY-----ISKPFKEEDLHSNIEMALHKHRT-EKKEIENS DSDE 137
MA2012 DY-----LKKPF DN RKLKTKLD TAR----- 118
MA2013-R1 YY-----ISKPLKKEKLLNI LEDIR----- 120
MA2445 DF-----LTKPINRLEL KTRVKSLL----- 117
MA2861 SL-----IQKRGDPK AQYSELSKRIWQIVKNGSG----- 126
MA3068 GY-----I IKPFQAPKVI E EIKKVIGA----- 120
MA4376 DY-----ISKPIDIHRFRSLIDKYLGE----- 121
MA4377-R1 YS-----FTKPVRRVELLDSLREIT----- 114
MA4377-R2 GHLISIMKKGTFGRKELINRIKQLA----- 123
MA4671 GY-----ISKPIDIDRFKLI LDTCTGGYQVL----- 127
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Figure S3: Amino acid sequence alignment of REC domain of all putative RR of *M. acetivorans*. Accession numbers of the employed sequences are listed in Supplement Table S4, for the alignment only the amino acid sequences of the REC domain were considered. The Alignment was constructed using CUSTAL Omega and modified using PowerPoint. All proteins share a conserved Asp residue, highlighted in bold with gray background.

Figure S4: TNP-ATP association kinetics of putative HKs. Constant protein concentration (2.5 μM, 5 μM or 7.5 μM) was mixed with variable TNP-ATP concentration (0 – 80 μM) in kinase buffer. A fluorescence emission spectrum in the range of 450 - 650 nm was recorded using a fluorescence spectrometer (FP-8300 fluorescence spectrometer, Jasco) and a quartz cuvette (SUPRASIL® cuvette, 3x3 mm, Hellma Analytics). The excitation wavelength was 410 nm, and the slit width was 5 nm. The fluorescence of TNP-ATP was determined as a maximum at 541 nm. The K_d value was determined using the SOLVER function of Microsoft Excel. (A.) TNP-ATP association kinetics of RdmS. (B.) TNP-

ATP association kinetics of MA2082. (C.) TNP-ATP association kinetics of MA2013. (D.) TNP-ATP association kinetics of MA4377. (E.) TNP-ATP association kinetics of PKR1R2.

Figure S5: Autophosphorylation assay of different putative HK. (A.) Autophosphorylation assay of RdmS under oxidizing (ox) and reducing (red) conditions. 10 μ M RdmS was incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with (+) or without (-) β -mercaptoethanol (β -me). **(B.)** Autophosphorylation assay of standard proteins and RdmS under oxidizing conditions. 10 μ M of the standard proteins albumin (ALB), alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH), β -amylase (β -Amy), carbonic anhydrase (CA) and RdmS were incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with (+) or without (-) β -mercaptoethanol (β -me). **(C.)** Autophosphorylation Assay of MA2082. 10 μ M MA2082 was incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with β -mercaptoethanol. **(D.)** Autophosphorylation Assay of MA2013. 10 μ M MA2013 was incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with β -mercaptoethanol. **(E.)** Autophosphorylation Assay of MA4377 and truncated protein variants. MA4377 produced in different *E. coli* strains and truncated variants (CHPK and PK) were incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with β -mercaptoethanol. **(F.)** Autophosphorylation assay of the MA4377 variants PKR1 and PK_{H497Q}R1. 10 μ M protein was incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with β -mercaptoethanol. **(G.)** Autophosphorylation assay of the MA4377 variants PKR1R2 and PK_{H497Q}R1_{D818N}R2. 10 μ M protein was incubated with $[\gamma\text{-}^{32}\text{P}]\text{-ATP}$ and the reaction was stopped using 4x SDS sample buffer with β -

mercaptoethanol. The samples of all assays were separated by SDS-PAGE and the radioactive signals detected by PhosphorImager (Autoradiogram). The same SDS gel was stained with Coomassie (Coomassie stained gel) to visualize the loaded protein.

Figure S6: Transphosphorylation assays of PK. Autoradiogram and corresponding SDS-PAGE (Coomassie stained gel) of the transphosphorylation reaction of different protein variants. Purified recombinant PK (10 μ M) was phosphorylated with [γ - 32 P]-ATP, after removing excessive ATP with illustra™ MicroSpin™ G-25 Columns (GE healthcare), the second protein was added in equimolar amount. **(A.)** Transphosphorylation assay with PK and R1. **(B.)** Transphosphorylation assay of PK with R2.

Figure S7: Putative further components of the phosphorelay of MA4377. **(A.)** Phosphorylation assay to test whether MsrX is receiving a phosphate from PK or R2. Transcriptional regulator MsrX is not involved in a phosphorelay. **(B.)** Phosphorylation assay to test whether MsrC is receiving phosphate from PK or R3. Transcriptional regulator MsrC is not involved in a phosphorelay.

Figure S8: Phosphotransfer profiling of MA2013 and MA2082. The purified HKs MA2013 and MA2082 are incubated with radioactive labelled ATP and then incubated with each of the purified RRs. The reactions were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and PhosphorImager. **(A.)** Phosphotransfer profile of MA2013 after 30 seconds. Transfer is visible for the REC-only RR MA2012. **(B.)** Phosphotransfer profile after 60 minutes. Transfer of phosphate was not clearly identified, possible transfer to MA2445 and MA1268. A signal around 80 kDa corresponds to the autophosphorylated kinase, a second signal corresponds to the transphosphorylated RR. **(C.)** Phosphotransfer profile of MA2082 after 30 seconds. **(D.)** Phosphotransfer profile after 60 minutes. A signal around 80 kDa corresponds to the autophosphorylated kinase, a second signal corresponds to the transphosphorylated RR. Transfer is not clearly identified, MA1468, MA1469, MA2012 and MA1366 might be involved in the phosphorelay.

Amino acid sequences of HK domains of putative HK and amino acid sequences of REC domains of RR of *M. acetivorans*.

>MA3405
NMSHELKTPPLNSIIGFSDLLKEEIAGPLNEKQSRVYQVFISSSGKNLLEIINDILDLSKAESGEEDLNVEKFSVDESINKVISV
VLPQAQEKNIILNYQSENRTLWITADEGKFRQIMENLLSNAIKFTPAGGSIDVTLKQEGLLVTVIEVKDTGIGIPEDSFEEKIFK
PFIQIDSSLSRNFEGTGLGLTLVKKYVEMHGGNIYVESKIGEGSSFRFELPVTR
>MA2294
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LTPPLASKKDIQILSVVDKELTTIRADRTKFKQILYNLVDNAIKFTHEDEGFIIVDARVEGDQAKIMVKDTGIGISKAGVKKIFQ
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LLSPASVKRITVELKIDPSVGNVRADITKLRQILYNLVSNAIKFTPAKQKVVISACKKEGVLEVKVSDTGIGLSKDSHEKIFM
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>MA1149
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>MA2555
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LSPIDRKMIEVQIQVDESNTIRADEARFAQIMYNLLDNAIKFSKENGLEVIDAKRKGDTVEITVKDYGIGIKVEDQSKLKF
PFSQIASFSSKKVQGTGLGLALVKQIVNLHGGYIWFNSRIGEGSTFAFTIPING
>MA1739
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LAPIADRKSIQIEIEVDSRLTNLYADEAKFAQIMYNLVDNAIKFASNSPVNVGARMKGDKVEITVTDIGAGIKPEDQHKLFK
PFSQVDYFASKQHGTGLGLYLKQIVQMRGYVWFRSVPGEKSTFAFAIPING
>MA3368
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LYPVADKKNIDIEIDMDELTKICADEEKFTTRIMYNLVDNAIKFSYENSLVKIGARKNGNLVEITVTDAGIGIKAEDQHKLFK
PFSQVNSFPSSKQGTGLGLSLVKQIVNLHGGYVWFRSEQEGESTFAFAIPAS
>MA2553
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PFSQIDSSFSKRYQGTGLGLALVKEIVQLHGGTVWFESEVVGKSVFGFSIPLPG
>MA4377
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LFLPLAQAKSLEINFVVGPDFGDIQADRSLIQILYNLVSNAIKFTPEGGRVSVYCKKSGSRALFSVTDGTGIGISSEDKKLFQ
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>MA2348
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LFPVFSKKKIRIEFEIGDGITTIYSDEGKQVQVLYNLVSNAIKFTEEGGFVKVSARKNGDMLQLSVKDTGIGITEEDLMKIFH
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>MA0777
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IEGEGARFEIKVPPGN
>MA1957
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>MA2256
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FKQINFALSREYESTGLGLVLSKNFVEMHGGRIWVESEPGKGSTFTFEVPVEI
>MA2013
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KAGSKGLKLAHFIEKDLPTSTFIDPVRKQVLFNLLGNAIKFTTKGGEIALSVEVYMPSENRSGLSNSDFPEEVALLFKVKDTG
IGIPPEKLSQIFDPFIQADASVTREYGGTGLGLAISQVLVMEGRVWVESEVVGKGTFTYFTVRVKR
>MA1270
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VSIKENEATVSYDSLPEIMADGTQLTQVFQNLISNAIKFRSKEAPKIHVSAEKEDDKWRFSVQDNGIGINPKYSEKIFEVFKR
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>RdmS
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>MsmS

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>MA0014

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>MA1269

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>MA2012

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>MA2013-R1

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>MA2861

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>MA3068

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>MA4376

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E

>MA4377-R1

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>MA4377-R2

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>MA4671

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